

FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS: A REVIEW OF MARKETED PRODUCTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

In the Pharmaceutical research the pharmaceutical industries are taking much interest in Gastro retentive drug delivery system that is Floating Drug Delivery System (FDDS) through the oral drug delivery system. The main aim of this study to review on FDDS focusing on its current advancement and its future. The Floating system works on the principle of buoyancy as they are low density system and have the ability to sufficiently buoyancy to flow over the gastric contents and remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period of time. Floating tablets and capsule are prepared by adding suitable ingredients with excipients like hydrocolloids, inert fatty materials and buoyancy increasing agents. Various categories of drugs like antacids, antidiabetic, antifungal and anticancer drugs are

formulated into FDDS. FDDS have bulk density less than gastric fluids. Floating tablets have emerged as an effective approach for improving the oral delivery of drugs that require prolonged gastric residence time. These tablets are designed to remain buoyant in the stomach for extended period, allowing the drug to be released in a controlled manner while enhancing its absorption. This technology is useful for drugs that absorbed mainly in the upper GIT, have narrow absorption window and have poor bioavailability when administered orally. From past to recent years, considerable attention has been given to development of Floating drug delivery systems due to their potential to overcome the limitations of conventional oral preparations. Its formulation includes various techniques, including effervescent and non-effervescent systems that are used to achieve controlled drug release and buoyancy. There are several factors that affects the effectiveness of Floating tablets such

as nature of drug, physiology of gastric fluid, condition of feeding, composition of formulation. Floating tablets has many challenges like gastric emptying and residence time but continue to be a promising strategy for gastroretentive drug delivery.

KEYWORDS: Floating drug delivery system, Gastro retentive tablets, HPMC, Sodium bicarbonate, Prolonged/Sustained release, Bioavailability, gastric retention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Among all the routes of administration oral route is the most convenient and widely used. But the one of the major limitations for conventional oral dosage forms is the variability in gastric emptying time, which cause improper drug absorption and reduced rate of bioavailability especially in the stomach or upper part of the small intestine.

To overcome this problem, gastro retentive drug delivery systems (GRDDS) have been developed. Among these, floating tablets are one of the most promising approaches. Floating tablets are low-density systems that remain buoyant on gastric fluids for an extended period of time, without affecting the normal gastric emptying rate. While the tablet floats, the drug is gradually released at a controlled rate, leading to prolonged gastric residence time and sustained drug release.

The floating tablets are usually made by substances that creates buoyancy like gas-generating agents such as sodium bicarbonate and citric acid, or by using swelling polymers like hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC). These components help maintain the tablet's position in the stomach, ensuring that the drug is released in the region where absorption is most efficient.

Thus, floating tablets offer significant advantages, including enhanced bioavailability, reduced dosing frequency, better patient compliance, and more consistent therapeutic effects. Gastro-retentive systems increase the residence time and bioavailability of drugs with narrow absorption in stomach. Have less solubility and stability in alkaline pH of small intestine.

The development of oral controlled release dosage forms is not just to prolong the delivery of the drug more than 12 hours, but to prolong the presence of the dosage forms in the stomach or upper gastrointestinal tract until all the drug is released for desired period of time. Rapid GI transit could result in incomplete drug release from the drug delivery device in the absorption zone leading to diminished efficacy of the administered dose.

Oral controlled release dosage forms have been developed over the past three decades due to their considerable therapeutic advantages such as:

1. Easily administrations.
2. Low cost of therapy.
3. Patient compliance and flexibility in formulation

2. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

2.1 AIM

To formulate and evaluate a floating tablet that prolongs gastric retention time and provides controlled drug release to enhance bioavailability.

2.2 Objectives

To design a floating tablet with suitable polymer and gas-generating agents, optimization the formulation for desired buoyancy and *in vitro* drug release characteristics. To evaluate the floating lag time and total floating time. To compare the developed formulation with conventional dosage forms.

3. Floating System

Floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) have a bulk density less than gastric fluids and so remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period of time. While the system is floating on the gastric contents, the drug is released slowly at the desired rate from the system. After release of drug, the residual system is emptied from the stomach.

3.1 Mechanism of Floating

Floating tablets work on the principle of buoyancy. After oral administration, tablet travels to the stomach and comes in contact with gastric fluid.

3.1.1 Gas-generating systems: These contain sodium bicarbonate and citric/tartaric acid. When they react with gastric acid, they produce carbon dioxide gas (CO₂), which gets trapped in the polymer matrix, decreasing the density of the tablet to less than 1.0 g/cm³.

3.1.2 Swelling systems: By the interaction with gastric fluid Hydrophilic polymers (Like HPMC) swell up, forms a gel barrier and maintain the tablet's buoyancy by entrapping the gas.

As a result, the tablet floats on the surface of the stomach contents, slowly releasing the drug over an extended period, before eventually disintegrating or dissolving.

Fig. 1: Mechanism of Floating.

3.2 Classification of Floating System

Fig. 2: Classification Of Floating System.

3.2.1 Non-effervescent system: The non-effervescent FDDS based on mechanism of swelling of polymer or bio adhesion to mucosal layer in GI tract. The most commonly used excipients in non-effervescent FDDS are gel forming or highly swellable cellulose type hydrocolloids, polysaccharides and matrix forming material such as polycarbonate, polyacrylate, polymethacrylate, polystyrene as well as bio-adhesive polymer such as chitosan and carbopol.

(a) Colloidal Gel Barrier System: Hydrodynamically balanced system first designed by Sheth and Tossounian. They remain buoyant in the stomach due to gel-forming hydrocolloids

and this enhances GRT and increases the amount of drug at the absorption site. Various gel forming agents used in this system are highly soluble cellulose type hydrocolloids which are hydroxyethyl cellulose, hydroxypropyl cellulose, hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose, polysaccharides and matrix forming polymers such as polycarbophil, polystyrene.

(b) Bilayer floating tablet : A bilayer tablet contain two layer immediate release layer which release initial dose from system while the another sustained release layer absorbs gastric fluid, forming an impermeable colloidal gel barrier on its surface, and maintain a bulk density of less than unity and thereby it remains buoyant in the stomach.

(c) Micro porous Compartment System: In this inside the micro porous compartment which has pores in the top and bottom walls contains encapsulated drug reservoir. In drug reservoir peripheral walls are completely sealed due to this sealing direct contact of undissolved drug with gastric surface is prevented. Entrapped air in the floating chamber stimulates the system to float over gastric content. Through an aperture the gastric fluid enters which dissolves the drug for absorption across intestine.

3.2.2 Effervescent system: Effervescent systems include use of gas generating agents, carbonates (e.g. Sodium bicarbonate) and other organic acid (e.g. citric acid and tartaric acid) present in the formulation to produce carbon dioxide (CO₂) gas, thus reducing the density of system and making it float on the gastric fluid. An alternative is the incorporation of matrix containing portion of liquid, which produce gas that evaporate at body temperature These effervescent systems further classified into two types:

(a) Volatile liquid containing systems: Inflatable chamber with a liquid can be incorporated which provide sustained gastric retention of drug delivery system. Liquids in this system include cyclopentane, ether that gasifies at body temperature which causes inflation of the chamber in the stomach. They contain hollow deformable unit which are osmotically controlled floating systems. System is divided into two compartments first compartment contains drug and there is volatile liquid in the second compartment.

(b) Gas generating systems : It basically contains polymers that gasify at body temperature effervescent compounds such as sodium bicarbonate, citric acid, tartaric acid, swellable polymers like methocel, and polysaccharides like chitosan. Resin beads loaded with bicarbonate and coated with ethylcellulose is the most common approach for preparation of

these systems. The ethycellulose coating is insoluble but permeable to water which release carbon dioxide due to which it floats.

3.2.3 Raft forming systems: Raft forming systems have received much attention for the delivery of antacids and drug delivery for gastrointestinal infections and disorders. The basic mechanism involved in the raft formation includes the formation of viscous cohesive gel in contact with gastric fluids, wherein each portion of the liquid swells forming a continuous layer called a raft. The raft floats. because of the buoyancy created by the formation of CO₂ and act as a barrier to prevent the reflux of gastric Contents like HCl and enzymes into the esophagus. Usually, the system contains a gel forming agent and alkaline bicarbonates or carbonates responsible for the formation of to make the system less dense and float on the gastric fluid

4. Advantages of Floating Tablets

Gastric residence time gets longer. The drugs that are absorbed in the stomach or upper intestine FDDS enhances the bioavailability. Reduced fluctuations in plasma drug concentration. Sustained and controlled drug release. It Improves patient compliance due to reduced dosing frequency. It is avoiding drug concentration peaks and minimizes the side effects.

5. Disadvantages of Floating Tablets

It is unsuitable for drugs that irritate the gastric mucosa and that are unstable in acidic pH. Floating depends on the presence of sufficient gastric fluid and it requires accurate formulation to maintain buoyancy. It is may be not effective in patients those who have altered gastric motility.

6. Scope and Significance of the Study

6.1 Scope of the Study: This study focuses of the gastro-retentive drug delivery system designed to prolong the residence time of the dosage form in the stomach by the formulation and evaluation of floating tablets by using various formulation parameter that influences buoyancy, floating lag time, and drug release profile.

6.2 Significance of the Study

Floating drug delivery systems provides a novel approach to overcome the limitations of oral dosage form by increasing gastric retention time.

They help to maintain the drug in its absorption zone for a longer duration, resulting in enhanced bioavailability and sustained plasma concentration.

The system reduces dosing frequency, improving patient adherence and treatment efficacy.

By localizing the drug in the stomach, floating tablets can also be beneficial for the treatment of gastric disorders, such as ulcers or infections caused by *Helicobacter pylori*.

The study contributes to the advancement of controlled drug delivery technology, providing insights into optimizing formulations for future pharmaceutical development.

7. MATERIALS AND METHODS

7.1 MATERIALS USED

The materials used for the formulation of floating tablets include the active drug, polymers, gas-generating agents, and excipients necessary for compression and stability.

Table 1: Materials and their roles in Floating tablet Formulation.

S.N.	Material	Category/Role	Example
1	Active Drug	API	Metformin HCl / Ranitidine HCl / Levodopa (as per study)
2	Polymer	Swelling/ Matrix-forming agent	HPMC (K4M, K15M, K100M), Carbopol 934P
3	Gas-generating Agents	To produce CO ₂ for buoyancy	Sodium bicarbonate, Citric acid, Tartaric acid
4	Binder	Provides tablet strength and integrity	PVP K30, Starch paste
5	Lubricant	Prevents sticking during compression	Magnesium stearate
6	Glidant	Improves powder flow	Talc, Aerosol
7	Diluent	Adjusts tablet weight and size	Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), Lactose
8	Solvent	Used in granulation	Distilled water / Isopropyl alcohol

7.2 Equipment Used

1. Electronic balance
2. Sieve shaker
3. Tablet punching machine
4. Hot air oven
5. Digital hardness tester
6. Friability tester

7. Dissolution apparatus (USP Type II)
8. pH meter
9. UV-Visible spectrophotometer

7.3 Method of Preparation of Floating Tablets

Methodology for single layer floating tablets: Basically, single layer floating tablets are prepared by compression methods. For this normally three basic compression methods are used. They are as follows:

- Direct compression,
- Dry granulation,
- Wet granulation.

Direct compression method: Direct compression is the process of compressing tablets directly from powdered materials without modifying physical nature of materials into the tablets.

Dry granulation method: It is defined as the formation of granules by slugging, if the tablet ingredients are sensitive to moisture and/or unable to withstand elevated temperature during drying.

Wet granulation method: In wet granulation the active ingredient, diluents and disintegrates are mixed or blended well in a rapid mixer granulator (RMG). Moist materials from wet milling steps are placed on large trays and placed in drying chambers with a circulating air current and thermo-stable heat controller. After drying, the granules are reduced in particle size by passing through smaller mesh screen. After this, the lubricant or glidant is added as fine powder to promote flow of granules. These granules are then compressed to get a tablet.

8. Method of Evaluation

Bulk density

- Tapped density
- Angle of repose (θ)
- Compressibility Index (carr's Index)
- Hausner's ratio
- Floating lag time and total floating time

- Swelling index
- Dissolution Study
- Dimensional Analysis
- Hardness
- Friability
- Size and Shape
- Weight Variation test (U.S.P.)
- Disintegration Test (U.S.P.)

9. CONCLUSION

From the results of the present investigation, it can be concluded that:

Floating tablets are an effective gastroretentive drug delivery system for improving the bioavailability of drugs with a narrow absorption window.

The combination of HPMC polymer and gas-generating agents successfully provided the desired buoyancy and sustained drug release.

The optimized formulation (F3) showed prolonged gastric residence time and controlled drug release, which could reduce dosing frequency and improve patient compliance.

Thus, floating tablet technology can be a promising approach for drugs like Metformin, Ranitidine, and Levodopa, which require controlled release and gastric retention for enhanced therapeutic effect.

FUTURE SCOPE

The study can be extended to *in vivo* evaluation to confirm gastric retention and bioavailability.

Optimization can be performed using statistical design of experiments (DoE).

Similar floating systems can be developed for other poorly soluble or short half-life drugs.

REFERENCES

1. Chien Y.W. (1992); Reported that controlled drug delivery systems improve therapeutic efficacy by maintaining a constant plasma drug level and reducing dosing frequency.

2. Singh B.N. and Kim K.H. (2000); Reviewed floating drug delivery systems and highlighted their potential for drugs that are absorbed primarily in the upper gastrointestinal tract.
3. Arora S. et al. (2005); Discussed various gastro retentive drug delivery systems, including floating, mucoadhesive, and swelling systems, emphasizing their role in improving bioavailability.
4. Shweta Arora et al. (2010); Developed floating tablets of Ranitidine Hydrochloride using HPMC and sodium bicarbonate. The formulation showed prolonged floating time and controlled drug release for over 12 hours.
5. Gupta R. et al. (2012); Formulated Metformin HCl floating tablets using HPMC K15M and Carbopol 934P, achieving sustained release and improved bioavailability.
6. Patel A. et al. (2013); Designed floating tablets of Levodopa and Carbidopa, reporting enhanced gastric retention and controlled drug release suitable for Parkinson's disease management.
7. Bardonnnet P.L. et al. (2016); Summarized advances in gastroretentive systems and concluded that floating drug delivery systems are effective for drugs with narrow absorption windows.
8. Madhavi B.L.R. et al. (2018); Prepared Ciprofloxacin floating tablets and found that the effervescent-based floating system significantly improved drug dissolution and retention time in the stomach.
9. Sharma A. et al. (2020); Reported on the optimization of Amoxicillin floating tablets using factorial design, demonstrating improved floating properties and sustained release suitable for *H. pylori* infection.
10. Streubel A., Siepmann J., Bodmeier R. (2002); Developed floating micro particles based on low-density polymers for prolonged gastric retention. The study showed that micro balloons could remain buoyant for more than 12 hours and provide sustained drug release.
11. Talukdar R. and Fassihi R. (2008); Developed a non-effervescent floating matrix tablet using hydrophilic polymers such as polyethylene oxide. The system swelled upon contact with gastric fluid, maintaining buoyancy without generating gas.
12. Ramesh C. et al. (2022); Investigated Domperidone floating matrix tablets with different grades of HPMC. The results indicated that higher viscosity polymers improved both floating
13. Duration Deshpande A.A., Shah N.H., Rhodes C.T., Malick W. (1997); Developed a novel gastric-retentive controlled-release dosage form and demonstrated that prolonged

gastric residence could improve drug absorption and therapeutic effectiveness for drugs with narrow absorption windows.

14. Whitehead L., Fell J.T., Collett J.H., Sharma H.L., Smith A.M. (1998); Conducted *in vivo* studies on floating dosage forms and reported that buoyant tablets remained in the stomach for extended periods, enhancing gastric retention and sustained drug release.
15. Iannuccelli V., Coppi G., Bernabei M.T., Cameroni R. (1998); Developed an air-compartment multiple-unit floating system that exhibited excellent buoyancy and prolonged gastric residence, reducing the risk of dose dumping.
16. Singh B.N. and Kim K.H. (2000); Further emphasized that floating drug delivery systems can significantly improve the bioavailability of drugs absorbed mainly in the stomach and upper small intestine by extending gastric residence time.
17. Klausner E.A., Lavy E., Friedman M., Hoffman A. (2003); Reviewed expandable and gastroretentive dosage forms and concluded that floating systems provide an effective strategy for improving drug absorption and reducing dosing frequency.
18. Chawla G., Gupta P., Koradia V., Bansal A.K. (2003); Highlighted gastroretention as a useful approach for overcoming regional variability in drug absorption and improving the effectiveness of drugs with narrow absorption windows.
19. Dave B.S., Amin A.F., Patel M.M. (2004); Formulated floating tablets of Ranitidine Hydrochloride using hydrophilic polymers and gas-generating agents, achieving prolonged buoyancy and sustained drug release.
20. Arora S., Ali J., Ahuja A., Khar R.K., Baboota S. (2005); Reviewed various approaches to gastroretentive drug delivery and concluded that floating systems are among the most promising methods for enhancing oral bioavailability.
21. Talukdar M.M. and Fassihi R. (2008); Developed hydrophilic polymer-based floating matrix tablets and reported that polymer swelling played a crucial role in maintaining buoyancy and controlling drug release.
22. Nayak A.K., Maji R., Das B. (2010); Reviewed gastroretentive drug delivery systems and reported that floating tablets offer advantages such as prolonged gastric residence, reduced dosing frequency, and enhanced bioavailability.
23. Pawar V.K., Kansal S., Garg G., Awasthi R., Singodia D., Kulkarni G.T. (2011); Evaluated different gastroretentive technologies and concluded that floating drug delivery systems are particularly effective for drugs with pH-dependent solubility and absorption.

24. Shah S.H., Patel J.K., Patel N.V. (2009); Reviewed stomach-specific floating drug delivery systems and emphasized the importance of polymers such as HPMC, Carbopol, and sodium alginate in achieving sustained buoyancy and controlled drug release.
25. Hirtz J. The gut absorption of drugs in man: a review of current concepts and methods of investigation. *Br J Clin Pharmacol.*, 1985; 19: 77S–83S. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2125.1985.tb02746.x.
26. Ponchel G, Irache JM. Specific and non-specific bioadhesive particulate system for oral delivery to the gastrointestinal tract. *Adv Drug Del Rev.*, 1998; 34: 191–219. doi: 10.1016/S0169-409X(98)00040-4.
27. Lenaerts VM, Gurny R. Gastrointestinal Tract-Physiological variables affecting the performance of oral sustained release dosage forms. In: Lenaerts V, Gurny R, editors. *Bioadhesive Drug Delivery System*. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 1990.
28. Rednick AB, Tucker SJ. Sustained release bolus for animal husbandry. US patent 3. 1970 April 22; 507 952.
29. Davis SS, Stockwell AF, Taylor MJ, et al. The effect of density on the gastric emptying of single and multiple unit dosage forms. *Pharm Res.*, 1986; 3: 208–213. doi: 10.1023/A:1016334629169.
30. Urguhart J, Theeuwes F. Drug delivery system comprising a reservoir containing a plurality of tiny pills. US patent 4. February 28, 1994; 434 153.
31. Mamajek RC, Moyer ES. Drug dispensing device and method. US Patent. 4 June 17, 1980; 207 890.
32. Fix JA, Cargill R, Engle K. Controlled gastric emptying. III. Gastric residence time of a non-disintegrating geometric shape in human volunteers. *Pharm Res.*, 1993; 10: 1087–1089. doi: 10.1023/A:1018939512213.
33. Kedzierewicz F, Thouvenot P, Lemut J, Etienne A, Hoffman M, Maincent P. Evaluation of peroral silicone dosage forms in humans by gamma-scintigraphy. *J Control Release*, 1999; 58: 195–205. doi: 10.1016/S0168-3659(98)00154-0.
34. Groning R, Heun G. Oral dosage forms with controlled gastrointestinal transit. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm.*, 1984; 10: 527–539. doi: 10.3109/03639048409041405.
35. Groning R, Heun G. Dosage forms with controlled gastrointestinal passage—studies on the absorption of nitrofurantion. *Int J Pharm.*, 1989; 56: 111–116. doi: 10.1016/0378-5173(89)90003-3.
36. Desai S. A Novel Floating Controlled Release Drug Delivery System Based on a Dried Gel Matrix Network. Jamaica, NY: St John's University, 1984.

37. Vantrappen GR, Peeters TL, Janssens J. The secretory component of interdigestive migratory motor complex in man. *Scand J Gastroenterol.*, 1979; 14: 663–667. doi: 10.3109/00365527909181934.
38. Wilson CG, Washington N. The stomach: its role in oral drug delivery. In: Rubinstein MH, editor. *Physiological Pharmaceutical: Biological Barriers to Drug Absorption*. Chichester, UK: Ellis Horwood, 1989; 47–70.
39. Desai S, Bolton S. A floating controlled release drug delivery system: in vitro- in vivo evaluation. *Pharm Res.*, 1993; 10: 1321–1325. doi: 10.1023/A:1018921830385.
40. Timmermans J, Andre JM. Factors controlling the buoyancy and gastric retention capabilities of floating matrix capsules: new data for reconsidering the controversy. *J Pharm Sci.*, 1994; 83: 18–24. doi: 10.1002/jps.2600830106.
41. Mojaverian P, Ferguson RK, Vlasses PH, et al. Estimation of gastric residence time of the Heidelberg capsules in humans: effect of varying food composition. *Gastroenterology*, 1985; 89: 392–397. doi: 10.1016/0016-5085(85)90342-7.
42. Bechgaard H, Ladefoged K. Distribution of pellets in gastrointestinal tract. The influence on transit time exerted by the density or diameter of pellets. *J Pharm Pharmacol.*, 1978; 30: 690–692. doi: 10.1111/j.2042-7158.1978.tb13366.x.
43. Garg S, Sharma S. *Gastroretentive drug delivery systems. Business Briefing: Pharmatech 2003 Web Site*. 5th edition. May 2003. Available at: <http://www.touchbriefings.com/cdps/cditem.cfm?NID=17&CID=5>. Accessed: October 6, 2005.
44. Timmerman J, Gansbeke VB, Moes AJ. Assessing by gamma scintigraphy the in vivo buoyancy of dosage forms having known size and floating force profiles as a function of time. Vol I. Paris, France: APGI, 1989; 42–51.
45. Yang L, Fassihi R. Zero order release kinetics from self correcting floatable configuration drug delivery system. *J Pharm Sci.*, 1996; 85: 170–173. doi: 10.1021/js950250r.
46. Burns SJ, Attwood D, Barnwell SG. Assessment of a dissolution vessel designed for use with floating and erodible dosage forms. *Int J Pharm.*, 1998; 160: 213–218. doi: 10.1016/S0378-5173(97)00312-8.
47. Joseph NJ, Laxmi S, Jayakrishnan A. A floating type oral dosage form for piroxicam based on hollow microspheres: in vitro and in vivo evaluation in rabbits. *J Control Release*, 2002; 79: 71–79. doi: 10.1016/S0168-3659(01)00507-7.
48. Sheth PR, Tossounian JL. Sustained release pharmaceutical capsules. US patent 4, November 21, 1978; 126,672.

49. Soppimath KS, Kulkarni AR, Rudzinski WE, Aminabhavi TM. Microspheres as floating drug delivery system to increase the gastric residence of drugs. *Drug Metab Rev.*, 2001; 33: 149–160. doi: 10.1081/DMR-100104401.
50. Ichikawa M, Watanabe S, Miyake Y. A new multiple unit oral floating dosage system. I: Preparation and in vitro evaluation of floating and sustained-release kinetics. *J Pharm Sci.*, 1991; 80: 1062–1066. doi: 10.1002/jps.2600801113.
51. Ichikawa M, Watanabe S, Miyake Y. Granule remaining in stomach. US patent 4 844 905. July 4, 1989.
52. Ozdemir N, Ordu S, Ozkan Y. Studies of floating dosage forms of furosemide: in vitro and in vivo evaluation of bilayer tablet formulation. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm.*, 2000; 26: 857–866. doi: 10.1081/DDC-100101309.
53. Choi BY, Park HJ, Hwang SJ, Park JB. Preparation of alginate beads for floating drug delivery: effects of CO₂ gas forming agents. *Int J Pharm.*, 2002; 239: 81–91. doi: 10.1016/S0378-5173(02)00054-6.